

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 36

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 36

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 36:0 For the choir director. <i>A Psalm</i> of David the servant of the LORD.</p>	<p>Psa. 36:1 לְמִנְצַחַת לְעֶבֶד-</p>
<p>Psa. 36:1 Transgression speaks to the ungodly within ¹his heart;</p>	<p>יְהוָה לְדָוָד : ² נֶאֱמַר-פִּשַׁע</p>
<p>There is ^ano fear of God before his eyes.</p>	<p>לְרָשָׁע בְּקִרְבַּ לְבָי אֵין-פֶּחַד</p>
<p>² For ¹it ^aflatters him in his <i>own</i> eyes Concerning the discovery of his iniquity <i>and</i> the hatred <i>of it</i>.</p>	<p>אֱלֹהִים לְנִגְדַ עֵינָיו : ³ כִּי-</p>
<p>³ The ^awords of his mouth are wickedness and deceit;</p>	<p>הִתְלִיק אֱלֹו בְּעֵינָיו לְמִצָּא</p>
<p>He has ^bceased to ¹be wise <i>and</i> to do good.</p>	<p>עֹוְנוֹ לְשִׁנָּא : ⁴ דְּבַר־יִפְיוֹ אָוֶן</p>
<p>⁴ He ^aplans wickedness upon his bed;</p>	<p>וּמְרִמָּה תָדַל לְהַשְׁכִּיל</p>
<p>He sets himself on a ^bpath that is not good;</p>	<p>לְהִיטִיב : ⁵ אָוֶן וַיִּחְשַׁב עָל-</p>
<p>He ^cdoes not despise evil.</p>	<p>מִשְׁכָּבוֹ יִתְיַצֵּב עַל-דֶּרֶךְ</p>
<p>Psa. 36:5 You're a lovingkindness, O LORD, ¹extends to the heavens,</p>	<p>לֹא-טוֹב רָע לֹא יִמָּאס : ⁶</p>
<p>Your faithfulness <i>reaches</i> to the skies.</p>	<p>יְהוָה בְּהַשְׁמַיִם חֲסִדֶךָ</p>
<p>⁶ You're a righteousness is like the ¹mountains of God;</p>	<p>אֲמוֹנַתְךָ עַד-שְׁתַּקִּים : ⁷</p>
<p>Your ^bjudgments are <i>like</i> a great deep.</p>	<p>צְדָקַתְךָ אֶכְתָּרֶי-אֵל</p>
<p>O LORD, You ^cpreserve man and beast.</p>	<p>מִשְׁפָּטֶךָ תִּתּוֹם רַבָּה אָדָם-</p>
<p>⁷ How ^aprecious is Your loving-kindness, O God!</p>	<p>וּבְהִמָּה תוֹשִׁיעַ יְהוָה : ⁸ מֵה-</p>
<p>And the children of men ^btake refuge in the shadow of Your wings.</p>	<p>יִקַּר חֲסִדֶךָ אֱלֹהִים וּבְנֵי</p>
<p>⁸ They ^adrink their fill of the ¹abundance of Your house;</p>	<p>אָדָם בְּצֵל כְּנָפֶיךָ יִחְסִיוֹן : ⁹</p>
<p></p>	<p>יְרוּיִן מִיֶּשֶׁן בֵּיתְךָ וְנַחַל</p>
<p></p>	<p>עַד־נִיף תִּשְׁקָם : ¹⁰ כִּי-עֲמֶךָ</p>
<p></p>	<p>מִקּוֹר תַּיִם בְּאוֹרֶךָ נִרְאָה-</p>
<p></p>	<p>אֹר : ¹¹ מִנְשֶׁךְ חֲסִדֶךָ לְיַדְעֶיךָ</p>

And You give them to drink of the ^briver of Your delights.

⁹ For with You is the ^afountain of life;

In Your light we see light.

Psa. 36:10 O continue Your loving-kindness to ^athose who know You,

And Your ^brighteousness to the upright in heart.

¹¹ Let not the foot of pride come upon me,

And let not the hand of the wicked drive me away.

¹² There the doers of iniquity have fallen;

They have been thrust down and ^acannot rise.

וְצַדִּיקֶתְךָ לְיִשְׂרָאֵל לֵב : 12 אֵל-
תְּבוֹאֲנִי רֵגֶל גִּבּוֹרָה וַיֵּד-
רְשָׁעִים אֵל-תִּנְדְּנִי : 13 שָׁם
נִפְלוּ פְעָלֵי אֲוֶן אֲחֵוּ וְלֹא-
יָכִלוּ קוּם :

References

<p>Psalm 36:1 ¹Another reading is <i>my heart</i> ^aRom 3:18</p> <p>Psalm 36:2 ¹Or <i>he flatters himself</i> ^aDeut 29:19; Ps 10:11; 49:18</p> <p>Psalm 36:3 ¹Or <i>understand to do good</i> ^aPs 10:7; 12:2 ^bPs 94:8; Jer 4:22</p> <p>Psalm 36:4 ^aProv 4:16; Mic 2:1 ^bIs 65:2 ^cPs 52:3; Rom 12:9</p> <p>Psalm 36:5 ¹Lit <i>is in</i> ^aPs 57:10; 103:11; 108:4</p> <p>Psalm 36:6 ¹Or <i>mighty mountains</i> ^aPs 71:19 ^bJob 11:8; Ps 77:19; Rom 11:33 ^cNeh 9:6; Ps 104:14, 15; 145:16</p> <p>Psalm 36:7 ^aPs 40:5; 139:17 ^bRuth 2:12; Ps 17:8; 57:1; 91:4</p> <p>Psalm 36:8 ¹Lit <i>fatness</i> ^aPs 63:5; 65:4; Is 25:6; Jer 31:12-14 ^bJob 20:17; Ps 46:4; Rev 22:1</p>	<p>Psalm 36:9 ^aJer 2:13</p> <p>Psalm 36:10 ^aJer 22:16 ^bPs 24:5</p> <p>Psalm 36:12 ^aPs 140:10; Is 26:14</p>
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Targum

Psa. 36:1 For praise. Of the servant of the LORD, David. ² Rebellion said to the sinner within my heart, “There is no fear of the LORD before his eyes.” ³ Because he flatters him with his eyes to find sins, to hate instruction. ⁴ The words of his mouth are wickedness and deceit; he has ceased to be wise in doing good. ⁵ Wickedness plots on his bed; he will take his stand in a way not good; he will not reject evil. ⁶ O LORD, your goodness is in the heaven of heavens, your faithfulness reaches to the skies. ⁷ Your righteousness is as high as the great mountains; your judgments are as deep as the great abyss; you will redeem both the sons of men and beasts, O LORD. ⁸ How precious is your goodness, O LORD; and the sons of men will dwell securely in the shadow of your presence. ⁹ They will drink deeply of the plenteous blessings of your house; and you will let them drink of your pleasant fountain. ¹⁰ For with you are streams of living water; in the splendor of your glory we will see light. ¹¹ Extend your goodness over those who know you; and your generosity over the upright of heart. ¹² May the foot of the proud not reach me; and may the hands of the wicked not make me wander. ¹³ There fell those who commit falsehood; they will be struck down, and will not rise again. --

Spiritual Awareness

The spiritual rewrite for the verses is in bold.

Introduction

This Psalm shows a stark contrast between people who follow the ways of the LORD and those who defy the LORD. The sage Radak said that the villain in this Psalm is Evil Inclination. Evil inclination is that spirit that drives people to do evil. David offers the philosophy that motivated the actions and attitudes of evil people in his day.

Superscript

For the choir director. A Psalm of David, the servant of the LORD.

Verse 1

אָמַר (n'um) means “to speak.” This word is a divine word. Therefore, the speaker is always the LORD. Several words in Hebrew are only used when the sentence is referring to the LORD.

An evil person tells him/herself that if the omnipotent LORD did not desire evil in this creation, He certainly would prevent it from happening. The LORD could also prevent evil from happening by making it unattractive. Thus, there is no fear that the LORD will do something to evil people. Therefore they commit their sins.

It is the LORD's pronouncement that transgression speaks to what is lawless in the heart; there is no of Gevurah before an evil person's eyes.

Verse 2

The wicked person believes that the LORD has paved the way for him/her to reach their sinful goals and pursue with bitter hatred anyone who might stand in his/her way.

For in his eyes, the LORD has smoothed the path so that he/she can attain their sinful goal and maybe hated.

Verse 3

More importantly, a sinful person uses their words to continue sin and conceal their true views and intentions.

The words of his mouth are violence and deceit; he has ceased to apply his mind to doing good.

Verse 4

Evil people spend their lives in the service of Evil Inclination. Even when they are sleeping, they plot how best to use their physical and mental faculties for evil purposes. An evil person plans to be on an evil path.

Even on his bed, he resolutely puts himself on the path to evil, and he does not scorn evil.

Verse 5

Chesed shines the LORD's loving-kindness from the Earth to the Heavens. The LORD offers his rules that train people in moral perfection and thus receive future salvation. Evil people do not understand that Evil inclination was given glamor only

to lure people. The LORD gave humanity the ability to practice evil by its own free will. Every person can refuse the temptations of Evil inclination.

O LORD, Chesed's loving-kindness reaches the Earth and extends back into Heaven.

Verse 6

The LORD knows that every generation of humanity still needs training on how to be righteous. Chesed is constantly sending its power to train humans.

The Sefirah Chesed is like the mighty mountains, and Your judgments are like the great deep; man and beast You will preserve, O LORD.

Verse 7

This verse is a parallelism of verse six. Chesed shines its power of loving-kindness upon the children of men.

The Sefirah Chesed shows the LORD's loving-kindness. The children of men find refuge in the shadow of Your wings.

Verse 8 & 9

The righteous received an abundance of delights from the LORD through the Divine Law and the sanctification of life, which they learn and attain. Wicked people may think that they are satisfied with the materialism of life. They will never understand that it is spiritual life that is better.

They satisfy themselves from the abundance of Your House, and You make them drink from the rivers of Your pleasures.

For with You is the fountain of life; in Your spiritual power, we see that power.

Verse 10

מִשְׁחַח חַסְדְּךָ (m'shoch chas'd'cha) – means “continue loving-kindness.” This phrase is generally used to express the prolonged deferment of fulfilling a promise or a stipulation.

Defer your loving-kindness to them that know You, and grant your righteousness to those that are upright in heart.

Verse 11

Defer your loving-kindness to them that know You, and grant your righteousness to those that are upright in heart.

Verse 12

Evil people may think that their abundance of fortune and power is true happiness. However, it is their path to hopeless destruction.

It is there that the works of violence have fallen; they have been thrust down and cannot rise.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

For the choir director. A Psalm of David, the servant of the LORD.

It is the LORD's pronouncement that transgression speaks to what is lawless in the heart; there is no of Gevurah before an evil person's eyes.

For in his eyes, the LORD has smoothed the path so that he/she can attain their sinful goal and maybe hated.

The words of his mouth are violence and deceit; he has ceased to apply his mind to doing good.

Even on his bed, he resolutely puts himself on the path to evil, and he does not scorn evil.

O LORD, Chesed's loving-kindness reaches the Earth and extends back into Heaven. The Sefirah Chesed is like the mighty mountains, and Your judgments are like the great deep; man and beast You will preserve, O LORD.

The Sefirah Chesed shows the LORD's loving-kindness. The children of men find refuge in the shadow of Your wings.

They satisfy themselves from the abundance of Your House, and You make them drink from the rivers of Your pleasures.

For with You is the fountain of life; in Your spiritual power, we see that power.

Defer your loving-kindness to them that know You, and grant your righteousness to those that are upright in heart.

It is there that the works of violence have fallen; they have been thrust down and cannot rise.

Appendix

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

